

Studies on some Coordination Complexes of Bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) Dichloride and Bis(cyclopentadienyl)zirconium(IV) Dichloride

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Bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) dichloride and bis(cyclopentadienyl)zirconium(IV) dichloride, when treated with the Schiff bases derived from the condensation of salicylaldehyde with *o*-aminophenol or *o*-aminothiophenol in a nonaqueous medium, form ionic complexes of the type $[\text{Cp}_2\text{M}(\text{L})]\text{Cl}_2$, where $\text{Cp} = \eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$, $\text{M} = \text{Ti}$ or Zr , $\text{L} = \text{salicyclidene-}o\text{-aminophenol (L')}$, $\text{salicyclidene-}o\text{-aminothiophenol (L'')}$. The secondary ligand reactions on these complexes resulted in a series of new complexes. In all these reactions the metal-ring bonds do not cleave. All the complexes have been assigned square-pyramidal geometries.

Schiff bases have gained importance because of the physiological and pharmacological activities associated with them¹. A number of workers have found that coordination of donor groups of ligand(s) to the Cp_2TiCl_2 and Cp_2ZrCl_2 moieties leads to the weakening of the metal-ring bonds². In the present communication we report the synthesis and reactions of some new complexes of Cp_2TiCl_2 and Cp_2ZrCl_2 with tridentate Schiff bases in order to evaluate the effect of coordination on the metal-ring bonds. These complexes have been subjected to cyclisation and secondary ligands addition reactions in order to study the mode of coordination of primary and secondary ligands to the central metal atom. It is observed that during the formation of complexes and their reactions the metal-ring bonds remain intact.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of $\text{Cp}_2\text{TiCl}_2/\text{Cp}_2\text{ZrCl}_2$ with Schiff bases in benzene and the reaction products of the complexes thus formed are presented in Fig. 1 and are represented by the following general equations :

where, $\text{M} = \text{Ti}$, Zr ; $\text{Cp} = \eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$; $\text{L} = \text{salicyclidene-}o\text{-aminophenol (L')}$, $\text{salicyclidene-}o\text{-aminothiophenol (L'')}$; $\eta = 1$, $\text{SL} = \text{ethylenediamine}$; $n = 2$, $\text{SL} = \text{morpholine}$ or pyridine ; $\text{Mac} = \text{macrocyclic Schiff bases}$.

These complexes are crystalline, high melting, dark brown, non-hygroscopic solids and are quite stable to aerial oxidation. Their elemental analyses are in agreement with 1 : 1 stoichiometry and the molar conductance values in nitrobenzene (PhNO_2) correspond to 1 : 2 electrolyte confirming the formulae assigned to the complexes (Table 1).

The ir spectra of the complexes show the usual peaks for the $\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$ groups, metal- C_5H_5 vibrations³ and phenyl groups. Conclusions about the bonding sites of metals with Schiff bases were arrived by the comparison of the important ir bands of the ligands and their complexes (Table 2). In the spectra of ligands L' and L'' , the absence of aldehyde group vibrations and presence of azomethine vibration indicate the formation of Schiff bases.

In the spectra of complexes 1A/B, the azomethine stretching vibration is seen with a positive shift

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Fig. 1

along with the lowering in wavenumber of ν_{OH} and $\nu_{C=O}$ vibrational frequencies. The complexes 5A/B also show a positive shift in the ν_{SH} and ν_{C-S} vibrations. All these shifts indicate the coordination of metal through all the three donor groups present in the ligands. The formation of the macrocyclic complexes 2A/B and 6A/B is supported by the absence of ν_{OH} and ν_{SH} vibrations in the respective complexes. In the spectra of secondary ligand(s) addition reaction products, bands due to OH or SH groups present in the basic skeleton of the Schiff bases do not show any significant shift which indicates their non-participation in the coordination and in their place the secondary ligands,

viz. morpholine, ethylenediamine or pyridine are coordinated as the bands due to these are observed at expected positions in the respective complexes⁴.

The far-infrared data of the complexes show metal-donor vibrations at 525–350 cm^{-1} . The assignment of these bands are done by a critical examination of the spectra with the help of literature⁵.

Chemical shifts for the protons of Schiff bases, their complexes and reaction products are given in Table 3. In the spectra of complexes, the existence of a sharp C₅H₅ resonance signal with a peak area of ten equivalent protons is attributed to rapid rotation of the ring about the metal-ring axis⁶. In the spectra

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Comp. no. *	Yield (%)/ m.p.(°C)	Analysis % : Found/ (Calcd.)				Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ mol^{-1}
		M	C	H	N	
L'	75 (137)	—	73.04 (73.23)	5.02 5.16	6.51 (6.57)	—
L''	82 (155)	—	68.02 (68.12)	4.69 4.80	6.02 (6.11)	—
1A	68 (210d)	10.19 (10.36)	59.62 59.76	4.91 4.98	2.96 (3.03)	56.02
1B	67 (225d)	17.95 (18.05)	54.52 54.62	4.48 4.55	2.71 (2.77)	54.36
2A	55 (>300)	9.76 (9.81)	61.41 61.49	4.66 4.71	2.79 (2.86)	57.62
2B	53 (>300)	17.04 (17.17)	56.41 56.47	4.28 4.33	2.56 (2.63)	55.98
3A	48 (190d)	9.07 (9.17)	57.39 57.48	5.49 5.56	7.98 (8.05)	58.82
3B	49 (255d)	16.09 (16.14)	53.01 53.08	5.02 5.13	7.38 (7.43)	58.61
4A	58 (>300)	7.48 (7.53)	58.42 58.50	6.29 * 6.33	6.25 (6.30)	58.30
4B	57 (>300)	13.37 (13.43)	54.69 54.77	5.71 5.74	6.09 (6.18)	53.17
5A	69 (227d)	9.98 (10.02)	57.67 57.75	3.96 4.03	2.64 (2.69)	52.55
5B	63 (215d)	17.41 (17.50)	52.83 52.95	3.96 4.03	2.59 (2.69)	52.76
6A	69 (>300)	9.45 (9.50)	59.48 59.54	4.52 4.56	2.70 (2.78)	58.88
6B	67 (>300)	16.61 (16.67)	54.74 54.82	4.13 4.20	2.49 (2.56)	57.37
7A	52 (>300)	8.81 (8.90)	55.69 55.77	5.32 5.39	7.71 (7.80)	55.38
7B	50 (>300)	15.59 (15.69)	51.55 51.62	4.91 4.99	7.05 (7.23)	54.17
8A	47 (>300)	7.48 (7.53)	62.18 62.27	4.82 4.87	6.52 (6.61)	52.69
8B	52 (>300)	13.37 (13.43)	58.21 58.30	4.45 4.56	6.09 (6.18)	53.08

* A : M = Ti, B : M = Zr.

of complexes 1A/B and 5A/B, the hydroxyl, azomethine and thiol protons are seen with coordination induced shifts (CIS) to lower field as compared to the respective free ligand, which clearly indicates the coordination of these groups with the metal. In the spectra of macrocyclic complexes 2A/B and 6A/B, the signals due to OH and SH protons are absent and an additional singlet due to CH₂ protons is seen confirming the cyclisation of complexes 1A/B and 5A/B.

In the spectra of the secondary ligands(s) addition products, the OH and SH proton signals do not show any significant shift as compared to the corresponding free ligands, indicating the non-participation of these groups in coordination. Apart from these the phenyl protons in case of complexes 8A/B are seen with increased multiplicity and peak area. In the spectra of complexes 3A/B and 7A/B, additional signals due to amino and CH₂ protons are seen around δ 4.45 and \approx 10 ppm as singlets, whereas

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT IR BANDS (IN cm^{-1}) OF COMPOUNDS

Compd no	VNH, VC-N	VOH, VC-O	VSH, VC-S	VC=N	M ← N	M ← S	M ← O
L'	1 300	3 480, 1 350, 1 220	—	1 600	—	—	—
L''	1 305	3 470, 1 350, 1 230	2 520, 1 020, 745	1 610	—	—	—
1A	1 285	3 310, 1 345, 1 210	—	1 610	395	—	470
1B	1 295	3 330, 1 345, 1 205	—	1 610	370	—	395
2A	1 290	—	—	1 610	395	—	470
2B	1 285	—	—	1 610	370	—	390
3A	3 200, 1 380, 1 280, 1 180	3 480, 1 350, 1 225	—	1 615	390	—	—
3B	3 210, 1 380, 1 285, 1 995	3 485, 1 350, 1 220	—	1 615	375	—	—
4A	3 220, 1 390, 1 275	3 485, 1 350, 1 230	—	1 610	395	—	—
4B	3 215, 1 385, 1 280	3 480, 1 350, 1 230	—	1 610	370	—	—
5A	1 275	3 310, 1 340, 1 205	2 535, 1 025, 755	1 620	390	465	380
5B	1 280	3 305, 1 340, 1 210	2 335, 1 025, 755	1 615	375	390	360
6A	1 285	—	1 025, 750	1 620	390	465	385
6B	1 290	—	1 030, 745	1 620	375	395	365
7A	3 200, 1 385, 1 295, 1 195	3 470, 1 350, 1 230	2 520, 1 030, 745	1 620	390	—	385
7B	3 200, 1 385, 1 295, 1 195	3 470, 1 345, 1 230	2 520, 1 030, 745	1 615	375	—	360
8A	1 290	3 470, 1 345, 1 230	2 520, 1 030, 745	1 620	390	—	380
8B	1 285	3 475, 1 340, 1 225	2 520, 1 030, 745	1 615	370	—	355

in case of complexes 4A/B, singlet due to amino protons along with two other multiplets at δ 2.75 and 3.50 due to N-CH₂ and O-CH₂ protons respectively are seen.

The formation of cyclised products is possible only when the two OH groups or OH and SH groups present in the basic skeleton of complexes lie in close proximity with each other. On the basis of steric factor that if both the cyclopentadienyl groups occupy axial positions it will hinder the coordination of the metal with donor groups of the ligands. So, in absence of X-ray data the proposed structure is square-bipyramidal on the basis of various physicochemical data.

Experimental

The molar conductance (10^{-3} M in PhNO₂) were measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge using dip type conductivity cell at $28 \pm 2^\circ$. Ir spectra (KBr/CsI/nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer (90 MHz) relative to TMS as internal reference. C, H and N were estimated microanalytically at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Titanium, zirconium and chloride were estimated by reported methods⁷. The purity of the products and completion of the reactions were checked by tlc.

TABLE 3-¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ) OF COMPOUNDS

Compd.	Phenyl protons	Cp protons	OH	SH	NH	CH	CH ₂
L'	8.10-6.80 (8H, m)	-	5.85 (2H, s)	-	-	2.10 (1H, s)	-
L''	8.10-6.85 (8H, m)	-	5.80 (1H, s)	5.00 (1H, s)	-	2.15 (1H, s)	-
1A	8.20-6.95 (8H, m)	6.70 (10H, s)	6.25 (2H, s)	-	-	2.75 (1H, s)	-
1B	8.25-6.95 (8H, m)	6.60 (10H, s)	6.25 (2H, s)	-	-	2.75 (1H, s)	-
2A	8.30-6.85 (8H, m)	6.65 (10H, s)	-	-	-	2.75 (1H, s)	2.05 (4H, s)
2B	8.50-6.80 (8H, m)	6.60 (10H, s)	-	-	-	2.34 (1H, s)	2.00 (4H, s)
3A	8.35-6.90 (8H, m)	6.70 (10H, s)	5.85 (2H, s)	-	4.45 (4H, s)	2.45 (1H, s)	2.10 (4H, s)
3B	8.35-6.90 (8H, m)	6.60 (10H, s)	5.85 (2H, s)	-	4.50 (4H, s)	2.45 (1H, s)	2.15 (4H, s)
4A	8.25-6.85 (8H, m)	6.70 (10H, s)	6.80 (2H, s)	-	4.40 (2H, s)	2.40 (1H, s)	2.75 (4H, m)
4B	8.20-6.85 (8H, m)	6.60 (10H, s)	5.80 (2H, s)	-	4.40 (2H, s)	2.45 (1H, s)	3.50 (4H, m)
5A	8.35-6.95 (8H, m)	6.70 (10H, s)	6.05 (1H, s)	5.20 (1H, s)	-	2.50 (1H, s)	-
5B	8.30-6.95 (8H, m)	6.65 (10H, s)	6.25 (1H, s)	5.20 (1H, s)	-	2.50 (1H, s)	-
6A	8.30-7.00 (8H, m)	6.70 (10H, s)	-	-	-	2.50 (1H, s)	2.05 (4H, s)
6B	8.30-6.90 (8H, m)	6.60 (10H, s)	-	-	-	2.50 (1H, s)	2.10 (4H, s)
7A	8.25-6.90 (8H, m)	6.75 (10H, s)	5.80 (1H, s)	5.00 (1H, s)	4.40 (4H, s)	2.45 (1H, s)	2.15 (4H, s)
7B	8.25-6.90 (8H, m)	6.60 (10H, s)	5.80 (1H, s)	5.00 (1H, s)	4.45 (4H, s)	2.40 (1H, s)	2.15 (4H, s)
8A	8.50-6.90 (18H, m)	6.70 (10H, s)	5.80 (1H, s)	5.05 (1H, s)	-	2.45 (1H, s)	-
8B	8.55-6.90 (18H, m)	6.60 (10H, s)	5.85 (1H, s)	5.05 (1H, s)	-	2.45 (1H, s)	-

Titanium tetrachloride (B.D.H.), zirconium tetrachloride (E. Merck) and all other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The solvents were dried and distilled before use by standard procedure. Cp₂TiCl₂ and Cp₂ZrCl₂ were prepared by reported methods⁸

Salicylidene-o-aminophenol (L') : To a methanolic solution of *o*-aminophenol (1.09 g, 0.01 mol), a methanolic solution of salicylaldehyde (1.05 g, 0.01 mol) was added with constant stirring maintaining a temperature of 60°. This mixture was refluxed for 6 h on a steam-bath and then filtered. The filtrate was concentrated and on addition of petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°), the ligand precipitated out which was crystallised from dry methanol (10 ml).

Salicylidene-o-aminothiophenol (L'') : Salicylaldehyde (1.05 g, 0.01 mol) in dry methanol (25 ml) was added to a solution of *o*-aminothiophenol (1.25 g, 0.01 mol) also in dry methanol. The mixture was stirred with constant heating maintaining the temperature at 60° for 3 h. The resulting yellow precipitate was washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) and dried under reduced pressure. The ligand was crystallised from dry benzene (10 ml) and dried.

Salicylidene-o-aminophenol-bis(cyclopentadienyl)-

titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV) dichloride (1A/B) : To a dry benzene solution (10 ml) of ligand L' (2.13 g, 0.01 mol), a dry benzene solution of Cp₂TiCl₂/Cp₂ZrCl₂ (2.48/2.92 g, 0.01 mol) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. The solution mixture was then filtered and on concentration of the filtrate, the resulting crude product was crystallised from benzene (10 ml) and dried in vacuo over P₄O₁₀.

Dibenzo(b,h)-1-aza-4,7-dioxocyclodeca-1-enebis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV)dichloride (2A/B) : To a solution of 1A/B (0.46/0.50 g, 0.01 mol) in dry benzene (10 ml) containing NaOH pellets (1.0 g), a solution of dichloroethane (0.20 g, 0.001 mol) in dry benzene (5 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The mixture was refluxed for ~10 h, then neutralised with dilute HCl, filtered and the filtrate concentrated to one-third of its original volume. To it a mixture of petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) and diethyl ether (1 : 2 ratio) was added and the resulting solid was washed with diethyl ether and dried in vacuo over P₄O₁₀.

Salicylidene-o-aminophenol-ethylenediamine/dimorpholine-bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV)dichloride

ium(IV) dichloride (3A/B, 4A/B) : To a solution of 1A/B (0.46/0.50 g, 0.001 mol) in dry benzene (10 ml), a dry benzene (10 ml) solution of ethylenediamine (0.06 g, 0.001 mol)/morpholine (0.17 g, 0.002 mol) was added, and the mixture was refluxed for 15 h and then filtered. The resulting solid upon addition of petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) to the filtrate, was crystallised from dry benzene (5 ml) and dried in vacuo over P₄O₁₀.

Salicylidene-o-aminothiophenol-bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV) dichloride (5A/B) : To dry benzene solution (10 ml) of ligand L'' (2.29 g, 0.01 mol), a dry benzene solution (5 ml) of Cp₂TiCl₂/Cp₂ZrCl₂ (2.42/2.92 g, 0.01 mol) was added and the solution was refluxed for 6 h and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to one-third of its original volume. The resulting solid addition of a mixture of petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and diethyl ether (1 : 2 ratio) was crystallised from benzene (5 ml) and dried in vacuo over P₄O₁₀.

Dibenzo(b,h)-1-aza-4-thia-7-oxocyclodeca-ene-bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV) dichloride (6A/B) : Anhydrous benzene solution (10 ml) containing 5A/B (0.47/0.52 g, 0.001 mol) and NaOH pellets (1.0 g) was added to a dry benzene solution (5 ml) of dichloroethane (0.30 g, 0.001 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 10 h. The mixture was then neutralised with dilute HCl, cooled and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to one-third of its original volume and a mixture of diethyl ether and petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) (1 : 2 ratio) was added and the resulting solid was crystallised from acetone (5 ml) and dried in vacuo over P₄O₁₀.

Salicylidene-o-aminothiophenol-ethylenediamine/dipyridine-bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV) dichloride (7A/B, 8A/B) : To a solution of 2A/B (0.23 g, 0.001 mol) in dry benzene (10 ml), was added a solution (5 ml) of ethylenediamine (0.06 g, 0.001 mol)/pyridine (0.16 g, 0.002 mol) in dry benzene, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for

8 h, then filtered and concentrated. The resulting solid on addition of petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) was washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and dried in vacuo over P₄O₁₀.

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